

**SOCIO-ECONOMIC, SPIRITUAL, AND CULTURAL
LIFE OF THE POPULATION OF THE TRASCASPIAN
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19481315>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 04th April 2026Accepted: 06th April 2026Online: 08th April 2026**KEYWORDS***Russian Empire, Turkestan
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churches, madrasahs, hospitals***ABSTRACT***The government of the Russian Empire, alongside its policies in all regions of Turkestan, also implemented necessary measures in the Transcaspian region to meet the spiritual, educational, domestic, and other social needs of the population.*

By 1881, following the abolition of local governance in this territory, the Russian Empire undertook a series of measures aimed at addressing the social issues of the population during the establishment of the Transcaspian region. In the cities of the Transcaspian region, infrastructure such as post offices, telegraph stations, the military governor's residence, officers' clubs, parks, residential buildings, military barracks, and church buildings were constructed. Among the essential urban structures, the construction of churches was considered a natural necessity.

The population largely consisted of adherents of Orthodox Christianity, although smaller religious groups were also present, including German Mennonites, Molokans, Old Believers, Baptists, Protestants, Catholics, Arians, and Khlysts.

The cities had a significant military presence, and soldiers, along with Russian civilians of various professions, performed religious rites and worship in a single church. Churches served as important public institutions that fulfilled the spiritual needs of the resettled population—such as naming ceremonies, marriage rites, baptisms, Christmas celebrations, and funeral services.

Organizations established by the Russian imperial government, such as the “Turkestan Eparchy” and the “Turkestan Department of the Holy Synod,” played an active role in organizing and financing the construction of churches and houses of worship, allocating substantial funds for this purpose. Archival sources preserve numerous letters sent by the Turkestan Department of the Holy Synod to the Governor-General of Turkestan¹. These letters emphasized the importance of building churches for the resettled Russian-speaking population, highlighting their role in meeting spiritual needs. They also addressed the allocation of 1–1.5 desyatins of land in villages and settlements inhabited by Russian

¹ National Archives of Uzbekistan, Fund I-1, List 9, Year 276, Pages 21, 22, 23, 24.

peasants for the construction of churches or prayer houses, as well as the involvement of engineers, builders, and designers in these projects².

An examination of financial allocations in 1910 shows that the Turkestan Eparchy received one of the largest shares of funding among the eparchies of the Russian Empire, second only to the Tobolsk Eparchy. A total of 176,312 rubles was allocated to the Turkestan Eparchy, intended for the construction of churches and prayer houses to meet the religious needs of the resettled population and to facilitate their permanent settlement in the region.

According to data from 1904, the religious composition of the resettled population in the Transcaspian region was as follows: out of 68,876 settlers, 27,623 were Orthodox Christians; among the rest were 8,293 Armenian Gregorians, 137 Armenian Catholics, 1,863 Roman Catholics, 1,013 Jews, 145 sectarians, 1,378 Baptists, and 1,580 Protestants³. In the city of Ashgabat alone, 5,507 Russian-speaking Christian residents were recorded⁴. The state primarily focused on constructing churches for the Orthodox majority, while smaller religious groups were generally limited to prayer houses.

The construction of Orthodox churches began in the 1890s, during the массовое resettlement of populations into the Transcaspian region, starting in the Mangyshlak district with the settlements of Fort Aleksandrovsk and Nikolaevsk. Initially, prayer houses were built in these settlements, where religious rites were conducted, and later full church buildings were established. These churches were constructed from fired brick based on designs typical of central губернии of the Russian Empire, with metal roofs, iron-gated entrances, doors on both sides, and large windows fitted with grilles to allow natural light. Special attention was given to making the interiors spacious and imposing⁵.

By 1892, there were 10 churches in the Transcaspian region: two in the Mangyshlak district (in Fort Aleksandrovsk and Nikolaevsk), three in the Krasnovodsk district (in Krasnovodsk city, Chikishlyar, and Uzun Ada), three in the Ashgabat district (two in Ashgabat and one in Kyzyl-Arvat), one in the Tejen district (in Sarahs), and one in the Merv district (in the city of Merv). In addition, small prayer houses existed in remote settlements without churches, such as Germob and Kozelnoye in the Ashgabat district⁶.

As of 1892, there were also three Armenian churches in the region—located in Ashgabat, Merv, and Kyzyl-Arvat. In Merv, where Jews lived in significant numbers, there was one synagogue and two prayer houses (molennas) where Jewish religious practices were conducted.

The financing of church construction came from three main sources: the state treasury, zemstvo funds, and private donations from benefactors. In the Transcaspian region, it is evident that churches for voluntary settlers were primarily funded by the state treasury. The Russian imperial government paid considerable attention to opening churches and constructing women's monasteries. It also ensured that churches were staffed with clergy—priests ("Holy Fathers"), assistants, deacons, bell-ringers, monks, and nuns.

² О Колонизации Туркестана//Речь.1908.-№46.

³ Review of the Transcaspian region 1904, Ashgabat, 1905, p. 3.

⁴ Review of the Transcaspian region 1892, Ashgabat, 1893, p.-18.

⁵ National Archives of Uzbekistan, I-961-fund, 1-division, 15589-volume, 45,46,47,48-sheets.

⁶ Review of the Transcaspian region 1892, Ashgabat, 1893, pp. 204-205.

Parish schools, as well as educational institutions for men and women, were established alongside churches. In some of these institutions, clergy provided instruction in religious subjects, and material support and proper living conditions were arranged for religious personnel.

Teachers working in schools affiliated with religious institutions received the following annual salaries in 1910–1912: 1,500 rubles in wages, 500 rubles for food, 250 rubles for clothing, and an additional 100–150 rubles for rent. Assistant clergy earned between 750–850 rubles, while deacons received 650 rubles annually. They also benefited from donations brought by peasants to the church.

Each year, parish schools and educational institutions attached to churches were allocated funds from the state treasury: 100 rubles for textbooks and teaching aids, 800 rubles for craft-related equipment, and 300 rubles for church maintenance. If a teacher lived in a rented or separate residence, an additional 500 rubles per year was provided for rent⁷.

In church-affiliated educational institutions, along with “Prayers to God” (religious instruction), students were taught moral education, arithmetic, geography, and the Russian language. These institutions primarily focused on basic literacy and were located either within church buildings or in separate facilities nearby. Students studied for 2–3 years, with classes organized either jointly or separately for boys and girls. In larger settlements, the number of students ranged from 120 to 150, in some cases reaching 190–200, while in smaller villages it ranged from 10 to 35, and at most 40–50 students⁸.

In conclusion, historical evidence shows that churches and prayer houses played an essential role in meeting the spiritual, moral, and everyday needs of the resettled Russian population.

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, various levels of educational institutions operated in the region, providing education to both the local population and the children of settlers.

It is well known that for centuries, a two-tier system of Muslim education existed for the indigenous population. The primary level consisted of maktab (elementary schools), usually attached to mosques, often comprising a single classroom and also referred to as *qorikhona* or literacy schools. Madrasahs, on the other hand, provided secondary and higher education.

At the instruction of General von Kaufman, the Russian academician A. Middendorf conducted a three-month inspection in Turkestan and noted the remarkably large number of schools and madrasahs, as well as the high level of literacy among the indigenous population, particularly their knowledge of the alphabet, which he considered exemplary. Concerned by such conclusions, the regional administration sought to bring all aspects of public life under control. In 1884, under the leadership of the third Governor-General N. O. Rosenbach, efforts were initiated to register Muslim educational institutions, mosques, and waqf properties, although this process was never completed⁹.

Russian authors such as V. P. Nalivkin, S. M. Gramenitsky, N. P. Ostroumov, A. P. Khoroshkhin, and others often deliberately portrayed traditional schools and madrasahs

⁷ Our colonization of Central Asia (Russian settlements in Turkestan) // Turkestan collection. Vol.429.-P.240-244.

⁸ National Archives of Uzbekistan, I-961-fund, list 1, volume 1878-fold, sheet 576, volume 1081-fold, sheet 89, back of sheet 89.

⁹ National Archives of Uzbekistan, I-47-fund, 1-ruykhat, 4112-yima volume, (1884), 11,12-sheets.

negatively, while failing to acknowledge the continued and even growing interest of indigenous youth in these institutions. Nevertheless, the development of a significantly renewed network of madrasahs became an important factor in the rise of national consciousness among the local population. It also contributed to the emergence of a stronger movement among the educated classes—not only for enlightenment but also for the political and social liberation of the Transcaspian region from colonial dependence.

While some high-ranking Muslim clergy supported the colonial authorities' anti-national policies, many wealthy individuals, landowners, and representatives of trade and industry actively contributed to the construction of madrasahs. As a result, by 1917 their total number in the region exceeded 440¹⁰.

From the early period following the establishment of the Turkestan Governor-Generalship, the regional administration attempted to restructure the hierarchy of Muslim clergy and impose administrative and political control over madrasahs and schools. Positions such as *shaykh al-Islam* and *qazi kalon* were abolished in major cities, and the jurisdiction of traditional courts—*qazi* courts for settled populations and *biy* courts for nomadic groups—was significantly restricted.

A key policy objective was to educate “loyal” and “pro-Russian” individuals from among the local population by opening Russian-native (Russo-native) schools for indigenous children, thereby preparing them for lower-level administrative roles.

However, the quality of education in these schools was often poor, with weak supervision of students, and in some cases the promotion of Great Russian nationalist views.

Before the October Revolution, the policy of gradually displacing traditional schools through administrative measures and expanding Russo-native schools as part of a broader Russification strategy proved largely ineffective. This was mainly due to excessive interference in madrasah activities and a dismissive attitude toward them by colonial authorities. Taking these and other factors into account, the Congress of Turkestan Muslim Teachers (May 20–23, 1917) advocated transforming Russo-native schools into national schools where instruction would be conducted in the native language, with Russian taught as a subject¹¹. Early proponents of the Jadid movement had already proposed such reforms during the initial establishment of new-method schools.

As the Jadid movement gained momentum in the region, reformers opened “*usuli savtiya*” (phonetic or new-method) schools, which enabled rapid literacy acquisition. Numerous studies in the history of Uzbekistan have addressed these developments, and research in this area continues. Under these conditions, Jadidism developed and strengthened primarily through its commitment to enlightenment ideals. The first new-method schools in the Transcaspian region were opened in the late 1880s, initially staffed by Tatar teachers. Given that N. P. Ostroumov served as Chief Inspector of Educational Institutions in Turkestan during this period and was directly involved in these developments, his accounts of the emergence of new-method schools in the cities of the Transcaspian region are considered reliable.

¹⁰ National Archives of Uzbekistan, I-47-fund, 1-division, 4213-volume, 16,17-sheets

¹¹ Туркестанский учитель, 1917, №1-2.-P.26.

The establishment of various types of schools in Russian settlements began in 1890, primarily as one- or two-grade literacy institutions. By 1910, ten such schools had been opened in the districts of the Transcaspian region, and by 1915 their number exceeded twenty, with most classes held in church buildings.

To ensure better social conditions for teachers sent to Russian settlements, their salaries and living conditions were improved. Teachers in educational institutions and parish schools received an annual salary of 1,500 rubles, along with 500 rubles for food and 250 rubles for housing. They lived in separate rooms within church buildings, school facilities, or rented private homes. The government allocated annual funds of 100 rubles for teaching materials, 300 rubles for craft equipment, 800 rubles for school maintenance, and 300 rubles for church-related needs¹².

By 1892, the Transcaspian region had 12 Russian schools and educational institutions, as well as one Armenian parish school attached to a church, with a total of 645 students of both genders¹³. At the same time, there were 163 Muslim schools with 2,429 local students.

Regarding secondary education during the Russian imperial period, notable examples include the Ashgabat male and female gymnasiums and the Merv vocational technical school. According to 1914 statistics, 519 students studied at the Ashgabat boys' gymnasium, 592 at the girls' gymnasium, and 133 at the Merv vocational school. Among the 133 students in Merv, 74 were Russian, 33 Armenian, 7 Jewish, 13 Persian, 4 Turkmen, 1 Khivan, and 1 German¹⁴.

As for primary education, in 1914 there were 72 lower-level schools in the region, including institutions in Tumanovsky, Vozelkovsky, Dmitrievsky, Komarovsky, Yablonovsky, Nizhne-Skobelevsky, Ashgabat, Fort Aleksandrovsky, Iolatan, Murgab, Khivaobod, Cheleken, Takhtabazar, Utamish, and others. These schools were mainly state-funded, with total annual allocations reaching 48,841 rubles as of January 1, 1915. The number of graduates from these institutions was 270 in 1912, 251 in 1913, and 392 in 1914.

In 1915, the ethnic composition of students in these schools included 3,688 Russians, 45 Poles, 60 Germans (Russian subjects), 210 Armenians, 2 Georgians, 16 Jews, 392 Turkmen, 139 Kyrgyz, 86 Persians, 49 Tatars, and 72 representatives of other nationalities¹⁵.

According to data from July 1, 1916, there were 186 national (indigenous) schools in the Transcaspian region: 30 in Ashgabat district, 33 in Krasnovodsk district, 50 in Tejen district, and 73 in Merv district. Of these, 1 was located in a madrasa building, 14 in rented premises, 84 in the homes of religious figures, 47 in private buildings, 25 attached to mosques, and 15 in communal houses¹⁶.

Teachers (mullahs) in these schools were trained in various locations: 111 in the Transcaspian region itself, 64 in Bukhara, 9 in Khiva, 1 in Iran, and 1 in a local Russo-native school.

After establishing the Transcaspian region, the Russian Empire also introduced measures to improve public health and implement modern medicine. The region's ecological conditions were particularly harsh. Due to poor water quality, the population suffered widely

¹² Our colonization of Central Asia (Russian settlements in Turkestan) // Turkestan collection. Vol.429.-P.243.

¹³ Review of the Transcaspian region 1892, G. Ashgabat. 1893, p.-191.

¹⁴ Review of the Transcaspian region 1916, Ashgabat, 1917, p. 284.

¹⁵ Review of the Transcaspian region 1916, Ashgabat, 1917, p. 237.

¹⁶ Review of the Transcaspian region 1916, Ashgabat, 1917, p. 225.

from diseases such as fever, malaria, dysentery, “Penda” ulcers, and leprosy, often leading to severe consequences.

The analysis of the socio-cultural life of the population in the Transcaspian region under the rule of the Russian Empire shows that colonial policy was aimed not only at administrative and economic control, but also at reshaping the spiritual, educational, and social environment of the region. The construction of churches, prayer houses, and parish schools played a central role in meeting the religious and everyday needs of the resettled Russian population, while simultaneously strengthening their permanence and influence in the region.

At the same time, the imperial administration sought to expand its ideological and political control through the education system. The establishment of Russo-native schools and the regulation of traditional Muslim educational institutions reflected a broader policy of Russification. However, these efforts did not fully achieve their intended goals. Despite administrative pressure and negative portrayals by some Russian authors, traditional makhtabs and madrasahs continued to function and even expand, contributing to the preservation of cultural identity and the growth of national consciousness among the local population.

The emergence and spread of Jadid schools further accelerated educational reform, promoting literacy, modern knowledge, and enlightenment ideas. This movement became a significant factor in shaping progressive thinking and strengthening aspirations for social and political change.

Overall, while the Russian Empire introduced certain elements of modern infrastructure, education, and healthcare, its policies in the Transcaspian region were largely driven by colonial interests. Nevertheless, local society demonstrated resilience by maintaining its cultural and educational traditions, which in turn laid the foundation for future national development and reform movements.

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